

AN ADVANCED RESIN TRANSFER MOULDING SYSTEM FOR THE PRODUCTION OF ADVANCED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY

The aerospace composites industry is using high-performance single-part epoxy resins for structural components. These are quasi-solid at ambient temperatures and need to be heated to reduce viscosity to processable levels. A new resin delivery system has been developed which is compliant with the critical requirements imposed by the aerospace industry.

Keywords: Resin Transfer Moulding, Epoxy, Aerospace, Microwave heating, Fuzzy Logic

INTRODUCTION

A number of aircraft components are being changed from metallic to composite materials [1] (Airbus A350XWB and Boeing 787 Dreamliner) in a drive to save weight and reduce operational costs. The manufacturing process for aircraft components must be made more efficient to ensure such aircraft are profitable to produce [2]. When manufacturing advanced composites the major cost factors are the labour required to prepare the materials for production, the material costs, and the processing costs [3]. This has generated a requirement for more automated resin processing equipment than is currently available in the market.

This paper briefly introduces the resin transfer moulding (RTM) manufacturing process, then considers microwave heating as a method for effective heating to achieve controlled reduction of the resin viscosity [4]. Further, this safety conscious industry imposes critical requirements for quality and recording of process parameters. The processing equipment discussed will utilise traditional proportional-integral-derivative (PID) control with the possibility of the use of fuzzy logic control (FLC) in the future.

RESIN TRANSFER MOULDING (RTM)

RTM is a process in which matched-mould tooling is used to manufacture components with good dimensional tolerances. This reduces or eliminates the need for shimming and filling in the final assembly which can be an issue for parts manufactured by other composite manufacturing technologies [3] which are then assembled into larger structures.

The RTM process consists of placing a (preformed) dry fibre pack into a matched mould tool. The mould surfaces are clamped together, sealing the cavity, and then resin is transferred into the mould either through positive pressure, vacuum or a combination dependent on the variation of RTM being used.

The major limitation of using such a system can be the size of the component. An injection pressure of 100kPa (1012mbar) in a mould with a surface area of 1m² requires a clamping force of 100kN. This presents some engineering challenges. One way of overcoming these challenges is to inject at low pressures. However, when producing high volume fraction (VF) components there may be a high restriction to flow which can result in the requirement for higher injection pressures. To achieve the required fill rate in high VF components, galleries or multiple injection ports can be used, reducing the time to fill and ensuring large structures can be infused within the pot life of the resin system.

The RTM system allows for Out Of Autoclave (OOA) processing. An integrally heated mould tool can reduce the 'bottle neck' caused by the use of autoclave cure. The components can be manufactured from similar resin systems to those used in pre-preg (pre-impregnated materials) and a potential cost saving of 50-75% can be achieved [3].

The success of the RTM process is reliant on two critical components; the mould and the resin transfer system. A well designed mould ensures that the entire component is properly infused and that no dry patches are left at the end of an injection. To ensure the component is manufactured to the required quality, the RTM injection machine must have good control over the required injection parameters i.e. heating, injection rate and injection pressures.

PROCESSING EPOXY SYSTEMS

Epoxy resin systems [2, 3] are available in numerous forms, and the chemical make up of such systems is outside of this study. For general applications, two-part epoxy systems are used. Inaccurate mixing of an epoxy and a hardener can severely affect the structural properties of the final component. Hence, in the aerospace industry there is a preference for premixed, pre-certificated one-part systems to ensure high quality in this highly safety conscious industry. When the resin is premixed by the resin manufacturer and processed by the specified method, the certificated resin should guarantee that the system provides the expected mechanical capabilities.

One-part systems often use a latent hardener, which is activated at a specific temperature. Typically, the resin viscosity is reduced at 80°C to a level permitting injection and complete fill of the mould without the fear of early cure. The temperature can then be raised to activate the hardener and (post-) cure the composite.

Single-part resin systems do however present secondary challenges, as the viscosity of the resin system at ambient temperatures is significantly higher than the limiting value generally agreed to be in the range of 800 mPa.s [5] to the "non injection point" at 1000 mPa.s [6]. Premixing the hardener and the resin system may start the curing reaction and limit the shelf life (storage period: typically 12 months at -18°C) and pot life (working life: typically between 1-24 hours at processing temperatures) [7].

Processing these resin systems also presents a number of challenges to the user:

- Long heating periods in ovens.

- Resin at temperatures which present risks to the operator during transfer and pouring.
- Low temperatures increase viscosity and could result in a blockage in the processing equipment, making flow through the fibre pack impossible.
- At the end of a production run, processing equipment that comes into contact with the resin system must be either disposable or cleaned.
- Bulk exotherm can occur when processing large volumes of epoxy resin systems in limited space. This occurs as the curing reaction of epoxy resin systems is exothermic and the material has low thermal conductivity. If a large volume of resin is heated in a confined space, the heat generated by the reaction can cause a chain reaction increasing the local temperature, in turn increasing the rate of reaction and the local temperature, until a point is reached where the resin can self ignite.

PROCESSING REQUIREMENTS

HEATING

As discussed previously, the temperature of a single-part resin must be raised to reduce the viscosity of the resin. For controlled industrial heating [8], options include electrical heating, hot fluids in pipes and microwave heating. Traditionally aerospace resin systems are heated in an oven or autoclave to the required temperature.

In conventional heating systems the rate of temperature rise in a material is limited directly by the thermal diffusivity and the surface temperature of the material. Thermal diffusivity is the combination of specific heat capacity, thermal conductivity and the density of the material [8]. In the processing of a system containing a latent hardener, there is the limitation that the surface temperature must not go above the hardener activation point. Hence, there should be no possibility of accelerating the temperature rise in the material by raising the surface temperature.

Dielectric heating methods, such as the use of microwaves, heat the whole volume of the resin simultaneously rather than relying on heat flow from the surface to the interior. Therefore, the rate of temperature rise within a material is less dependent on the materials thermal diffusivity.

Microwave Heating

A microwave field causes electrostatic coupling of dielectric materials with the high frequency microwave electric field [8]. This coupling causes the dipoles to continually re-align themselves and physically oscillate [9]; the frictional forces between the molecules generate heat throughout the material. This provides a volumetric heating system where the whole mass of a body is heated to the same temperature at the same rate. It is a relatively efficient heating method as it only heats dielectric materials. Thus, if the cavity is manufactured from a non-dielectric material, it will not be heated by the microwaves. This results in both a reduction in processing time and energy/costs.

Thermal Runaway

A major problem when heating resin with microwaves is the danger of 'hot spots'. If the temperature of the resin rises above the activation temperature the resin system will begin to cure. If curing was to occur within the preheating or degassing chamber, there is the possibility of a runaway reaction.

To reduce the possibility of 'hot spots' occurring, the microwave cavity must be designed in such a way as to reduce the possibility of 'standing waves' (the cause of localised heating). A mode stirrer is the most common method of ensuring uniform heating [11] and can take numerous forms. A standard metal stirrer can effectively change the reflective nature of the cavity.

Meyer and Herbeck [9] investigated the effect of microwave preheating on the Hexcel RTM6 epoxy resin system and found that the microwaves had no undesirable effect on the viscosity of the resin or the structural integrity of the manufactured component. It was also found that 10kg of resin could be heated from ambient to 80°C in 25 minutes, compared with traditional heating methods which take approximately 240 minutes; this gives a preheating time saving of ~90%.

The heating of resin systems produces a major 'bottle neck' in the production of advanced composites; microwave heating provides an opportunity to greatly increase the manufacturing rate. Therefore a system that incorporates microwave heating could allow continuous manufacturing capabilities.

DEGASSING

Resin 'degassing' is a fundamental requirement for the manufacture of advanced composite components [12]. The removal of gaseous components prior to injection reduces the likelihood of voids, which can weaken the structure if present within the final component [7].

In the composite manufacturing process the resin is placed in, or transferred to, a degassing chamber and a vacuum of approximately 90 mbar [12] is applied to the chamber for a period specified by the manufacturer of the resin system.

RESIN TRANSFER SYSTEM

This section introduces a number of different methods of transferring resin from the machine into the mould. It discusses the strengths and weaknesses of each pumping system and the challenges they present to the processing of single-part resin systems. In RTM there are two principal methods for transferring the resin from the preheating/degassing chamber to the mould:

Pressure Pot

The pressure pot is the simplest method [7] of injecting single component resin systems. A vacuum is generated in the pressure pot, to draw resin via the pressure differential into the pot. The resin can then be degassed, and then pressurised for injection.

An alternative type of pressure pot system works on the basis that the operator places a resin manufacturer's original container directly into the degassing chamber, the resin is

then degassed and pressurised for injection. The latter system reduces the effort involved in the clean up stage, but there is a limitation to the size of component that can be produced. The major limitation to the pressure pot system is that the flow rate cannot be directly controlled. Flow rate can only be controlled by adjusting the pressure in the pot and balancing it against the resistance to flow presented by the fibre pack in the mould.

Positive Displacement Pumps

The use of a pump is the most common method of transferring fluid materials in industry and there are three types of pump commonly used in manufacturing thermosetting composites. Positive displacement pumps work on the principle of displacing a fixed amount of fluid from the suction port of the pump to the outlet of the pump. The positive displacement pump can be categorised into two main subcategories 'reciprocating' and 'rotary'. Reciprocating type pumps are more efficient than rotary type pumps and are less affected by the viscosity of the pumped medium and the back pressures produced in the system.

Single Acting Piston Pump

The single acting piston pump is a reciprocating type pump similar to a syringe [13]. In one direction the pumped material is drawn into the pump cavity, and when the pump is driven in the opposite direction, resin is forced out of the pump cavity.

An alternative system requires the operator to manually remove the piston from the cavity to allow resin to be poured into the pump cavity. The piston is replaced, a vacuum is generated in the remaining cavity to degas the resin, then the piston is actuated displacing the resin into the mould. This common method for injecting single component resin systems allows the injection to both be controlled via pressure and flow rate. Flow rate can be inferred from the rate at which the piston is displaced.

A limitation of such a system is that pumping cannot be continuous as the pump must be refilled after each injection process. Cleaning such a system automatically can present difficulties, and therefore trying to automate a manufacturing process using this transfer method would present challenges.

Double Acting Piston Pump

Double acting piston pumps work on a similar principle to that of the single acting piston pump. They pump on both the upstroke and the down stroke, allowing the output to be continuous. In composite manufacturing where two components must be 'meter-mixed', these pumps are highly efficient and, hence, are a preferred option.

There are two concerns when considering this type of pump for pumping single component resin systems. Firstly there are a number of areas where resin can build up, and therefore, trying to automatically clean a system is challenging. Secondly, this type of pump has a non-linear output and therefore the pump changeover at stroke-end presents a control system with some challenges.

Gear Pump

The gear pump is a rotary positive displacement pump. The fluid is transferred around by toothed gears. The gears mesh forcing the fluid out of the discharge port. Although the internal geometry is highly toleranced, it is possible for material to 'slip' back through the gap between the outer casing of the pump and the gear surface.

Due to its simplicity the pump can be easily flushed, however, the pump is susceptible to solid contaminants within resin systems which can result in wear, reducing the tolerance between the gears and the housing, and in turn reducing the efficiency of the pump.

With simple and complete control over flow, combined with the ability to provide continuous flow and a flushable system, the gear pump provides a solution that is suitable for processing any size of composite component. Although having a lower efficiency than the other two pumping systems, the use of flow meters can permit tight closed-loop control of flow.

CONTROLLING THE SYSTEM

Every industrial system must have some level of control. This can be in the form of open-loop control, where the systems action is designed in such a way that the outcome can be assumed, or a closed loop system, which is designed to be reactive to the response of the system it is acting upon.

In composite component manufacturing there are both systems in place. For example a system using one of the reciprocating positive displacement pumps can be efficient enough for the user to assume that the quantity of resin pumped is directly proportional to the total displacement of the pump.

However, in a heating system it cannot be assumed that, by introducing a set amount of thermal energy, the required temperature will be achieved. In a temperature management system, closed-loop control should be used. The energy input into the system can be related directly to the process temperature and the target temperature.

Within a resin injection process there are three main parameters that must be controlled; the resin temperature, resin flow rate and injection pressure.

The Control Requirements

An injection machine for advanced composites must have full closed-loop control and respond to feedback from the system. The two key control technologies are PID and FLC.

Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) Controller

The PID controller accounts for the vast majority of industrial controllers [14] and is capable of controlling linear systems, such as heaters and pumps. The RTM injection process, using a gear pump, can be viewed as a simple linear pumping system and it presents few challenges to a PID controller.

Fuzzy Logic Controllers (FLC)

For a deeper discussion of FLC [15, 16] should be consulted. Fuzzy logic controllers have the advantage of being able to control linear and non-linear systems. Although less commonly used for industrial control systems, proportional-derivative type fuzzy logic is a

common implementation of FLC [16]. FLC also allow for systems to be controlled with a limited understanding of the process. Enabling the ‘rule base’ of the controller to be developed empirically rather than having to mathematically model the system to develop a controller.

Controlling the injection

The one-dimensional case of Darcy’s law (Equation 1) [4] allows the direct implication of flow rate and injection pressure to be visualised.

$$v = \frac{1}{\mu \epsilon} k \Delta P \tag{Equation 1}$$

v : Linear flow rate k : Permeability ΔP : Pressure gradient
 μ : Viscosity ϵ : Porosity

If a constant flow rate is applied to a system where the extent of fill is increasing (as areas of the preform become saturated), assuming constant resin viscosity and permeability, it can be shown that the back pressure within the mould will increase. When the pressure is controlled to be constant the flow rate will reduce as the injection progresses.

Problems can arise when controlling an injection using feedback from either just pressure or flow rate. If flow rate is kept constant throughout an injection there is the possibility that the pressure within the mould cavity will rise to a level that could result in forces greater than the mould clamp or equipment can withstand. If the injection is controlled under a constant pressure system there is the problem that at the start of the injection the flow rate into the mould can be so great that flow can cause “fibre wash” displacing the fibres within the preform.

The ideal injection system, therefore, would begin an injection under flow control ensuring there is no fibre wash and then at a preset point, automatically switch over to pressure control. This intelligence can be pre-programmed into a programmable logic controller (PLC) which allows a fully integrated control system to achieve the required solution.

Figure 1: Representation of pump control system

Figure 1 represents a controller for the injection of a mould, depending on the requirement of the system, the transducer can either be a flow meter or a pressure transducer in the machine or within the mould cavity, the set point can be of the corresponding feedback type i.e. flow or pressure. A tuned PID or FLC can be used to control the drive and therefore directly control the output of the pump. A number of these controllers can be integrated into a PLC program, and control can be switched from flow to pressure control automatically.

THE INJECTION MACHINE

The study has identified different technologies for heating and pumping resins, and different methods that can be used to control an injection process. The following section introduces an RTM injection machine currently under development.

The aim of the machine is to be “user friendly”. This requires that the machine is safe, easy to use, ergonomically sound, and requires little effort to clean at the end of an injection. The machine must also be efficient, keeping the use of resin, energy and consumables to a minimum.

Figure 2: (a) Flow of resin through machine (b) CAD model of proposed machine

Figure 2a is a representation of the machine and identifies all of the fundamental modules within the machine, the arrows represent resin flow. Figure 2b is a computer assisted design (CAD) representation of the prototype machine currently under development.

A Modular Approach

To ensure the machine is suitable for aerospace composite component manufacturers, the system must be able to process varying quantities of resin, at different rates. A modular approach has been taken, allowing the manufacturer to specify the required throughput of the machine and the maximum quantity of resin the machine can process.

The quantity of resin the machine can process is directly related to the size and number of degassing chambers. To reduce the risk of bulk exotherm the size of the degassing chambers do not exceed the size specified by the resin manufacturer.

The maximum throughput of the machine is related to the maximum flow rate of the pump in use and the rate at which the temperature of the resin can be increased. For a continuous operation the output of the pump must not exceed the rate at which the resin temperature can be raised. However, if the operation is discontinuous the heating rate of the machine can lag the output of the machine, as long as the degassing chambers provide the system with the required buffer.

Heating

Within the machine there are two types of heating: Microwave heating, provides fast, efficient pre-heating and can result in a machine with a greatly increased level of throughput.

Electrical heating, provides simple temperature maintenance capabilities and can ensure the resin temperature stays constant during degassing and transfer through the machine.

Transferring Resin within the Machine

To reduce the level of risk involved in processing the resin systems, an automatic transfer system has been designed. The system will transfer the heated resin from the microwave heating chamber to the degassing chamber via a heated hose and flushable transfer valves. This will reduce any risk associated with the manual transfer of resin between preheating ovens and degassing chambers often found on current machines. The use of flushable transfer valves allows for a reduced amount of time spent in the clean up stages of a production cycle.

Pumping System

A gear pump transfers the hot degassed resin from the degassing chamber(s) into the mould. The gear pump is controlled through a control system with feedback from a flow meter and a pressure transducer on the machine; with the option of integrating in mould sensing into the control of the machine. This allows the machine to be programmed so that pump control can be run using both pressure and flow feedback, and automatically switch between the two when required.

The advantage the gear pump presents is its simplicity, it is driven by an AC servo motor and has a linear output, this allows for simple PID control or more advanced FLC control. The pumps simple construction also allows for a flushable system, therefore, reducing the manual effort required at the clean up stage of the manufacturing process.

Control

The output of the machine is currently controlled through a PLC running PID controllers for temperature and pump management; the aim is to move some of the pump control from PID to FLC, allowing the machine to deal with any non-linearity that may occur within a system.

The machine will monitor the injection process and continually feedback the injection parameters to the operator through a supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) system running on an industrial PC. At the end of an injection the SCADA software will produce a report summarising the injection process.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper has introduced the manufacturing of advanced composite components using RTM, and discussed the requirements of a machine for processing single-part epoxy resin systems.

The paper has identified suitable injection strategies for producing RTM components. It considers different control methods including fuzzy logic controllers and proportional-

integral-derivative controllers. The prototype machine will be controlled using PID controllers with an aim to move to FLC further on in the development cycle.

The project presents the possibility of a new generation of RTM injection machines suitable for processing advanced composite materials. It offers a fully modular approach allowing advanced composite component manufacturers to specify a machine to match their production requirements and ensures that the operator's health and safety are taken into consideration. Work continues on the development of a prototype and product launch is planned for October 2009.

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